

Sociological and Economic Causes of 'County Lines' Drug Dealing

George Donaghey

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16911487 | ISSN: 2977-1676

The Journal of
Crime & Justice
Dissertations

About: The Journal of Crime & Justice Dissertations (JCJD) is an online platform for student dissertations. The JCJD is a London Metropolitan University [Crime Lab project](#) which was established in 2023.

The JCJD does not make use of a peer-review process as is typical with standard academic journals. Rather the JCJD serves as a platform for showcasing high-achieving student dissertations that relate to the concepts of social justice and social harm. All dissertations are sourced from reputable universities and all dissertations have received a 1st class grade. The JCJD makes use of an inspection process but this is only to ensure that the minimum requirements of the platform are upheld (it is not a peer-review process). JCJD publications should be read in this context, the publications are students' work and should not be used in the same manner as rigorously peer-reviewed content. For a full disclaimer regarding the JCJD and for more details regarding the inspection process for dissertations, please visit the website journalcjd.org.

Director (Editor in Chief): Shaun S. Yates.

Executive Committee: Ellada Larionidou, James Alexander, Emek Yuce Zeyrek-Rios, Eden Zaidner, Denise Morrison, Xingwei Li, Isifu Mwase, Kevin J. Brazant, Elina Konstantinidou, Karen Dyer, Elaine Isadora Thomas, Ronke Shoderu, Finley MacDonald, Katrina Ozcakil Mozova, Corinne Funnell, Wendy Akpareva and Anthony Schembri.

Address: London Metropolitan University, 166-220 Holloway Road, London, N7 8DB.

www.journalcjd.org

British Library Registered ISSN: 2977-1676

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16911487>

© 2025 by The Journal of Crime & Justice Dissertations (JCJD).

The Journal of
Crime & Justice
Dissertations

Acknowledgements

Thank you to Matus for guidance, and my Mother for love.

Abstract

This paper is an amalgamation of historical and contemporary criminological theory, with the aim of creating connections throughout time periods to define the causes of county lines in both a sociological and economic context. Taking the *nurture* side of *Nature vs Nurture* discussions, both peer and environmental interactions shape a person into a deviant being; they are who their social and ecological environment is. If these individuals are surrounded by economic deprivation, the strain (to achieve financial success) they experience is accentuated by a lack of opportunity. County lines is proved here to be that escape from poverty: a business model built out of exploitation and the manipulation of an individual's introspective moral code, which has now been displaced by the deinstitutionalisation of migration and isolation. Even looking at labelling theories in a historical context, impoverished people have never been encouraged to be conformists to common law. They are instead inspired to take life by the reins, and manipulate their national environment for their own financial gain, with complete disregard to human rights and modern slavery legislation, and to fight against social norms that have hindered them. Clamping down on these regulations and encouraging multi-agency work to prevent the exploitation of children, would create a better policing framework to tackle county lines at a national scale. This would fix legislative problems, but not the true cause: disproportionate, relative deprivation. It is clear that redistribution of wealth and greater support for those experiencing poverty would practically eliminate the need to deviate into county lines. This would stop child exploitation in organised crime groups, and alleviate the population of a growing drug use and distribution epidemic.

Contents Page

Acknowledgements	1
Abstract.....	2
Contents Page	3
Chapter 1: Introduction	4
Chapter 2: Methodology.....	6
Chapter 3: Sociological Relations between County Lines and the People.....	8
Chapter 4: Economic Strains on those Legitimising their Illegitimate Businesses	13
Chapter 5: Understanding Both Sociological and Economic Interpretations in Contemporary Theories Relating to County Lines Itself	19
Chapter 6: Further Discussion & Conclusions.....	23
References	27
Appendices.....	38

Chapter 1: Introduction

Under the *Policing and Crime Act 2009*, gang-related drug dealing is defined as the “*unlawful production, supply, importation or exportation of a controlled drug*” (35[7a]) by three or more individuals, who can be identified by others as part of a group (34[5a-b]). *County lines* drug dealing has more criteria: referring to a mobile phone, connected to a specific number associated with a drug dealing organisation, being passed from cities to more rural areas of the United Kingdom (O’Hagan and Long 2019; Williams and Finlay 2019; Spicer 2021). Areas in East Anglia, such as Norfolk and Suffolk, are particularly affected due to their efficient transport links- ones that county lines organisations utilise to their advantage (O’Hagan and Hamis 2023). Members of the organisation follow, setting up a headquarters in said rural town (the *host town*) to receive an importation of narcotics from a home city. These so-called businessmen collect drugs from the host city (London, eg.) to drop them off at host towns (unsaturated markets) for local dealers with good community relations to sell at a microscale (May et al. 2005; Coomber and Moyle 2012). Better transport links means it is easier to import drugs into a community and supply the dealer therein (ergo the prominence in Norfolk and Suffolk). Class A drugs- especially crack cocaine and heroin- are normally distributed via this method (Coomber and Moyle 2017; Wilson 2017; Black 2020). Importation and sometimes distribution of the drugs involve young people who are groomed and forced into slavery through intimidation, violence, and/or debt bondage (Stone 2018; Wroe 2021). These victims are mainly 15-17 year old boys, paired alongside the elderly and vulnerable to be used for *cuckooing* (Olver and Cockbain 2021). *Cuckooing* refers to the use of a vulnerable person’s premises to conduct illegal activity, without the informed consent of the owner via manipulation (Cooper et al. 2017; Stone 2018). Under new definitions, county lines can be considered a form of modern slavery, forcing and exploiting unpaid minors into distributing a service (ibid.; Modern Slavery Act 2015). This third-party distribution is done on the basis of supply and demand. Supply and demand is a topic in theoretical economics spanning the entire length of economics itself, discussing the philosophy of the idea (Thornton 1866; Gale 1955). The idea thereof is that a successful business’ supply never exceeds stock, fitting perfectly into our example of an oversaturated drug market in large cities, such as London (Windle and Briggs 2015; Black 2020). With a smaller amount of stock, the supply is slowed in order to maintain manageable stock levels. For example, if there is a large amount of drugs in London, the law of supply and demand dictates that exportation to smaller communities (where there is a slower supply chain) is more beneficial economically (Thornton 1866; Windle and Briggs 2015). This is due to the fact that the price of goods rises when there is more of a demand (Gale 1955); one piece of evidence supporting this idea in our

context is that the number of crack users has depleted a third in the last year, following a common trend over the last 25 years (ONS 2024). Something to note is that between 2019 and 2021, there was an anomalous rise in crack users (ibid.). Alongside this, the price of crack cocaine has followed, slowly decreasing each year as demand dwindles and spiking again in the years 2019-2021 (UNODC 2006; 2021). This is clearly related to economic strategies used to maximise profits: the less buyers, the lower the cost. This is the basis of county lines. County lines has not gone unnoticed by locals, having a great effect on vulnerable communities and children (Andell and Pitts 2018; Williams and Finlay 2019). The use of children in county lines is imperative to its nature- mimicking large corporations that exploit the masses for profit (Antonopoulos and Hall 2014). Hereby, children are groomed into slavery. Without the use of children, organised crime groups (OCGs) would have to evolve past these methods and county lines would become less profitable (ibid.). It is also obvious that exploitation of children is very upsetting to a closed community. Adults are less likely to fall into modern slavery (Home Office 2021b), so adult exploitation is uncommon. There is also more support for these victims to prevent slavery (ibid.). This exploitation itself is often misconstrued, with many victims of cuckooing being regular drug users that create a mutually beneficial relationship (Coliandris 2015; Andell and Pitts 2018). These drug users themselves could be considered a problem to society- a "*social misery*" (Valentine and Fraser 2008, p. 410). Drug addiction harms the finances and social status of a whole family (Andlin-Sobocki 2005), bringing negative aspects into small towns where there is a strong social cohesion. Drug use perpetuates poverty, having been born therefrom (Acker 2010; Manhica et al. 2020), causing a town to suffer greatly (Kaestner 1997). The whole country is affected, with drug abuse costing the NHS £650 million a year (Home Office 2021a). With the majority of Class A drugs being supplied by county lines (Black 2020), national savings could be made from stopping it. Drug use is also prevalent in homelessness (Kemp, Neale, and Robertson 2006), damaging subcultural societies. It is evidently clear that there are many problems that stem from Class A drug use, all of which could be greatly slowed by tackling county lines.

Chapter 2: Methodology

Doing a research project based on my future employment strides with the police guided my topic selection for this dissertation. It was fitting that I chose a policing and crime-oriented topic based on UK legislation. County lines and drug crimes in general are common in policing legislation, so it seemed natural. Having recently seen a documentary on the impact of county lines, it inspired me to choose this as my topic. All of my sources were found online, mainly via *Google Scholar*, incorporating published books with articles on economics and criminological theories. This is reliable as all the work I found has referenced official studies, alongside being valid sources themselves. Most sources here come from academic articles or published books, both of which are produced by well-known companies. Some articles I have found did not have enough sources, or were published from unreliable companies; therefore, I did not use them. However, there is always a possibility that these papers themselves had biases within them, affecting their results and thus affecting my conclusions. For example, Marx (1863) was very judgemental of capitalist societies and his papers are one-sided as a result. The theories mentioned in this dissertation are the most relevant to my question, as they are all economic theories of crime, or sociological ones. I originally had a focus on how sociological causes affect financially-based crimes, but that topic was too broad. The crimes I was originally focusing on, including white collar crimes, were irrelevant to most sociological theories too. Not only this, but some theories were too vague and could be used to explain most crimes, with disregard to financial-specific ones. An example of this is psychological positivism. This dissertation would be too long if I included every theory that has a tablecloth explanation for most crimes. By looking at a zonal model of the whole country, it could be found that crime (especially county lines) originates from cities, such as London and Glasgow, hence their importance. Other theories mentioned, such as Marxist criminology and left-realism, are directly related to how poverty causes financially-based crime: it was a natural progression to mention these. It surprised me how much Merton's theories (1938; 1954; 1968) were relevant to county lines, but the more I read about them, the more I wanted to incorporate them into this paper. My timeline originally was between the 17th Century, and the 1990's, disregarding contemporary theories. This would make my dissertation less reliable as county lines is a relatively new development in drug dealing. It would be impractical, and nearly impossible, for me to do primary research, due to the violence within drug dealing (Antrobus 2009). It would also be entirely unethical and dangerous for me to interview, study, and chart members of county lines gangs. Participant observation methods would also be disapproved by gang members and the invisibility of their work (Bryman 2016; Curran 2023). Not only that, but the geographical scale would mean a study of multiple counties- something that is not viable for me in the

given timeframe and resources. The only ethical issue I feel could affect this paper is my own personal bias. I truly believe deprivation causes most crimes, therefore I am going to subconsciously be more lenient towards theories supporting my views. This is an innate belief of mine, and could ethically affect this project. Within this bias itself is another factor affecting validity of my explanations; the criticism of the United Kingdom as a capitalist state is purely theoretical, as the UK has never been a communist country. Therefore, there is no controlled variable to compare the criticisms to. This being said, my sociological chapter appears resultantly unbiased.

Chapter 3: Sociological Relations between County Lines and the People

The age-old question of *nature vs nurture* is inexplicably easy: a criminal is not born (Sousa and Sousa 2021). They are shaped into a deviant being through a multitude of different environmental influences and peer interactions. There is not a linear connection between a single cause and deviancy- it requires multiple sources to push someone to immoral behaviour (Bloch 1958; Monahan 1961). How someone interacts with their environment will entirely shape their behaviour and attitudes towards social norms. Most importantly, these interactions change the introspection and internal morality of criminals, building new moral codes to abide by themselves (ibid.; Merton 1938). Once institutionalisation of collective morals fails, these learnt and self-fabricated morals will reign a criminal; we should not understand county lines as deviant in our own legislative terms, but legitimate in their twisted moral complex (Agnew and Passas 1997). Classical schools of criminology were developed in 18th Century Europe, birthing substantial advancements in understanding crime types and trends (Valasik 2014). Coined by Augustus Comte at the turn of the century, theorists Bentham and Beccaria led the way for classical criminology, showing crime to be hedonistic and risk-averse (O'Brien 2008; Burke 2019). The general theory was that criminals evaluate a pain-pleasure principle, deciding whether the risk of punishment was worth the gain of committing a certain crime (ibid.). This suggests that crime is committed under free will and rationality (Roshier 1989), taking place in a political, economic, and social context. These are the sociological bases to be focused on in this dissertation. Financial-based crimes, such as drug dealing, are deeply hedonistic. Even looking at theories that are centuries old (classical criminology), this view links heavily to county lines culture and its high-roller lifestyle. Studies have shown that county lines dealing creates a cycle of hedonism; carefree and pleasure-centred lifestyles create economic crimes, which in turn generates opportunities for more fun, delinquent activities and thus the cycle continues (Taylor and Potter 2013; Felson 2018). This is not without contradictions. Wilson (1975) noted that an improvement in quality of life still led to an increase of crime in the 1950s and 1960s, despite classical thoughts being with the antithesis. It is important to mention this, as this paper cannot be done without reference to the many criticisms of leftist theories on crime.

Merton touched upon this economic deprivation in his 1938 paper, *Social Structure and Anomie*. This is a groundbreaking paper, revolutionising the way we connect community bonding to crime. There are two main theories Merton worked on, often indistinguishable from each other (Featherstone and Deflem 2003). His theory on *anomie* is an important sociological step. Communities have shared goals

and expectations of each other, creating cohesion within subcultures, and at a macroscale (Merton 1938; Bernburg 2002). *Anomie theory* looks at how crime rates increase in societies without this cohesion. The deinstitutionalisation of cultural goals and crumbling social connection leads to *anomie* in individuals: the feeling of alienation from norms (Agnew and Passas 1997; Featherstone and Deflem 2003; Brown 2022). Assimilation into these goals is important, as it creates a sense of belonging and decreases the likelihood to deviate; when an individual is isolated and misunderstands what is unacceptable, deviant behaviour occurs due to a lack of understanding (Merton 1938; 1968; Agnew and Passas 1997). This deviance is built on two subtheories. One side suggests that anomic individuals form their own social norms individually, insinuating that what they do is acceptable to them internally: a sort of anti-assimilation (Merton 1954; Brown 2022). This influences crime as it challenges the way of the world, and further brews anomie between individuals and society. The other theory behind anomie-inspired deviance is that those individuals are experiencing alienation due to closed-mindedness and uneducation (Achterberg et al. 2017). Modern analysis of anomie theory shows high levels of uneducation in alienated individuals (ibid.). In terms of county lines, truancy and exclusion is a specific element that allows kingpins to spy vulnerable children to indoctrinate (McAra 2004; Temple 2020). This information connects uneducation, which can be caused by school exclusion, to anomie; in essence, the alienation of individuals from societal norms begins when they regularly or indefinitely miss school. This then leads to county lines. Naturally, there are other connotations of truancy that can be exploited by gangs. Apathy of the victim's parents, or exposure to crime at a young age, teaches the child these subcultural norms that stray from community expectations (Stone 2018; Brown 2022). This means the child would be more lenient to commit crime. This theory on parental apathy invalidates the link between truancy and anomie mentioned (as uneducation is listed as a vital reason for anomie), but it allows further explanation of county lines' child exploitation. However, if the child is learning from their parents' deviant behaviour, it supports Merton's idea of accommodating subcultural, deviant norms (Merton 1938; Brown 2022). When we interpret anomie in terms of modern England, there is a clear lack of social cohesion in a political and ecological aspect. Goodhart (2017) noted that there are high levels of anomie in cities, due to its mobile population and rapid advancement. These people dislike how fast cities progress, akin with those experiencing anomie with early industrialisation (ibid.; Brown 2022; Han, Ren, and Zhang 2022). These people are also more likely to adopt their own theologies, following suit with Merton's assumptions on anti-assimilation. Goodhart's (2017) assumptions are supported by sociological positivist studies on both Britain and America.

Beside industrialisation, there was a vital inquiry into the economic state of London and its relation to crime. Charles Booth's *Inquiry into Life and Labour in London (1886-1903)* is a staple point in ecological

theories of crime (Booth and Reeder 1984). While the study's focus was economic, the connotations therein are of sociological relations between a person and their environment. Booth presented a map of Victorian London, colour-coding areas of crime and class- which overlapped heavily. The underclass were keyed as "*vicious, semi-criminal*" (LSE 2024), with the working class noted alike as desperately hedonistic (Orford et al. 2002). We know drug dealing is linked to exposure to poverty as a child and adult (Dunlap et al. 2010; Manhica et al. 2020). Keys such as Booth's shows this is a known fact for over a century, increasing the validity of our findings. There are even studies dating back to 1862, on the high crime rates in *rookeries*: a colloquial term which now means slums (Mayhew 1862). These keys predetermine our subconscious biases on the links between poverty and crime. If it is historical in society to subconsciously assume the underclass is criminal, then how can we challenge it progressively? We must understand instead how the environment shapes them and not their finances, taking a step away from Booth's assumptions of poverty. There are a few studies disproving the assumption that the poor commit crimes based on their economic status. The first ecological theory comes from Burgess and Park (1915) and their *concentric zonal model*, also known as *Chicago School theory*. Chicago School was formed in 1892, taking inspiration from Comte, a positivist, and Durkheim the sociologist (Walklate 2017). Thus, the term *sociological positivism* was coined (ibid.). This means sociological phenomena were researched empirically, focusing on hard evidence and a scientific approach. Chicago School was the first to suggest that social interactions with the environment is the cause for crime, opening an influential gap in criminology to be discovered (White and Haines 2004). Park and Burgess were part of the second generation of the first school, acting as a staple point for many theories to come (Lutters and Ackerman 1996). Even now, we look at relations between smartphones and criminals to understand their interaction with their environment ecologically (Hoeben et al. 2014). The zonal map Park and Burgess produced shows high levels of anomie in the outer ring of central Chicago, with its constantly mobile population and industrialisation (Lutters and Ackerman 1996; Sampson 2019). While this is inapplicable for a vast amount of crimes, the links between anomie and county lines shows concentric zonal models apply to drug dealing. It's substantial to note that the focus of the zonal model was on sociological relations to an individual's environment, and not economic ones. When cross-referencing a map of county lines host towns in reference to supplying routes from London (*Fig. 1*) with a national map of social housing (*Fig. 2*), we can see a direct correlation between high concentrations of social housing and the locations of host towns. This creates a concentric map of the UK in terms of county lines, proving Chicago School theory to be applicable here. All of this evidence seems very compelling when cross-referenced with anomie theory, but some studies disprove its utility. When looking at Sheffield, Baldwin and Bottoms (1976) found no link between zones of transition and crime. There was no zonal pattern. Business areas themselves actually had higher levels of crime, with

little to no economic deprivation involved therein. Their findings showed that it was environmental influences within different areas that influenced crime: for example, estates created moral disambiguation within their subculture (ibid.). Social disorganisation was also a listed cause of crime in Sheffield.

Similarly, Shaw and McKay (1942) looked at how poverty affects juvenile delinquency in their *social disorganisation theory*. This is directly relational to county lines and the use of child exploitation. In the inner city, poverty and mobile populations were high. Ergo, anomie reigned and caused crime (ibid.; Bellair 2017). The findings focused on the interactions between individuals and their deprived environment: not the actual deprivation itself. Rapid change leads to rapid decline (Wilson 1987); sudden ethnic variety in heterogenetic cities and economic revolutions led to deinstitutionalisation of values (Shaw and McKay 1969). To counteract this deinstitutionalisation in children, consistent peer groups and internalisation of family values is required (ibid.). Peer groups are often varied and constantly changing in anomic societies, hindering this internalisation (ibid.; Durkheim 1951; Bellair 2017). These findings link social disorganisation theory to county lines, based on ecology. Social disorganisation theory also discusses how a lack of proximity to the crime leads to neutralisation of guilt and fear (Sykes and Matza 1957). This is vital to understanding county lines and the use of children. Distancing oneself from a crime leads to moralisation of the crimes one is committing, thus increasing the frequency thereof (Cohen 2001). Accountability and guilt are responsible for the pain/pleasure principle that goes into drug dealing. Denial of responsibility reduces risk of getting caught, leading to riskier and more frequent crimes (Sykes and Matza 1957; Lacey 2007). With the use of a third-party- in this case, children- deniability of responsibility can be plausible, allowing the mastermind to get away with the crime (ibid.; Stone 2018). Criminals therefore trick themselves into believing the crime they are committing is distanced and ergo morally correct, leading to neutralisation (Fingarette 1969; Costello 2010). They cannot see the effects and undergoing of their crime, so they lose moral interest. Those who run county lines could also see themselves as vigilantes, taking control of the economic constraints that trap them (Lazarsfeld and Merton 1954; Taylor and Potter 2013). They see county lines as a legitimate business trading goods, with genuine employees. Neutralisation is naturally reduced by a lack of definitive values and goals in a society; ergo, anomic areas cannot provide juvenile delinquents with morals to override neutralisation of guilt (Sykes and Matza 1957). Shaw and McKay (1942) provided a small amount of empirical research into areas of anomie, leading Sykes and Matza (1957) to have little evidence to run off. This is a hindrance to our understanding. Their later, empirical revision (Shaw and McKay 1969) could have been used to increase the validity of Sykes and Matza (1957), unfortunately having never left another revision of neutralisation. However, later Chicago-esque

studies theorise that the place in which a crime takes place is not the cause of the crime, but a conscious choice made by the criminal to justify the pleasure/pain principle by reducing the risk of being caught (Cornish and Clarke 2008). These studies contradict Park and Burgess' (1915) thesis and provide a seemingly cloudy area for defining the ecological causes of county lines. We know county lines occurs in certain areas due to their ecology (great transport links, economic deprivation, etc.), but also the clientele (O'Hagan and Hamis 2023). It could be said that Park and Burgess' theories therefore cannot be applied to county lines, but I would argue otherwise. The focus of their original study was anomie and how it affects crime rates. We can also look to Shaw and McKay (1942) for support, as they find interactions with economic deprivation to influence crime and not the deprivation itself. Combining these two assumptions, Park and Burgess have a good grasp on the occurrence of county lines: anomie is the main cause.

Ecological theories stretch as far as proving county lines as a rare exception to common rules, supporting the view that zonal theory relates to county lines. For example, most offending takes place with short distances travelled (Bernasco 2014), with a study on Sheffield proving that offenders travelled 3km on average to commit crime (Wiles and Costello 2000). This completely contradicts the very nature of county lines, and the long distance travelling required to import drugs. This means interpretation of theories have to be contemporary, understanding that contradictions may not apply directly to county lines. These theories would be incomplete without Merton's interpretations of anomie and how it affects society: the deinstitutionalisation of values leads to an apathy towards morality and law. It can be contained within individuals, who may also seek out others to justify their means as legitimate. There is nothing more important to understanding county lines than the idea of anomie. It is the deinstitutionalisation that first plants the seed of delinquency in children, evolving into more serious crime as new social norms become internalised and assimilated. It is vital to remember, though, that this anomie comes from a multitude of places- especially economic deprivation.

Chapter 4: Economic Strains on those Legitimising their Illegitimate Businesses

Being a crime with an “*unrelenting drive for profit*” (Coomber and Moyle 2018, p. 10), county lines is greatly influenced by the economy. Individuals personally experiencing economic deprivation live a completely different life to those who were born into opportunity to create socially accepted businesses; they must adapt to their surroundings and rebel against social norms to legitimise themselves as entrepreneurs in the crime world. To understand their drive to validate themselves in a hypocritical society, we must understand how the economy they are brought up in shapes them as people. Interactions with deprivation are what separates deviants from conformists. These interactions are based on numerous things, ranging from greed and jealousy, to consumerism in the current political structure in the UK.

Internationally renowned as a sociological theory, Merton’s *strain theory* (1938) could not be more closely linked to economics and how it affects crime. While there are some sociological aspects, it should be heralded as an economic, leftist theory on lines with Marxism. Strain theory suggests that crime occurs when juveniles see wealthy people and assume unachievable dreams set upon them by the media and the world around them (Özbay 2003). This is called the *American Dream* (Merton 1938). They wish to achieve middle-class status and idolise money, with some claiming this greed forces juveniles into crime (Agnew 1995). This is most likely due to a lack of anomie; in fact, it is the institutionalised goal to gain financial independence from one another that causes greed. This achievement is unobtainable by lower-class individuals without exploitation of the submissive (Merton 1938). This directly correlates to county lines’ exploitation of children as workers. The *American Dream* is easily achievable when exploitation is utilised for financial success, usually through modern slavery (UKPGA 2015; Wroe 2021). Not only does it relate to this aspect, the whole basis of drug dealing culture and wealth perpetuates crime (Taylor and Potter 2013). Merton recognised this greed and focused his strain theory thereupon. It is not the person who creates the crime, but the financial position they find themselves in (Merton 1938; Özbay 2003). Agnew et al. (1996) specifically found a link between monetary dissatisfaction and frequency of income-producing, drug-related offences. This is irrefutable evidence that Merton’s strain theory (1938) can directly explain county lines. The combination of exploiting children and monetary dissatisfaction creates a solid explanation; despite this, there are

many criticisms of Merton's groundbreaking theory. A lack of legitimacy in his claims is that most studies focus on working-class crimes. Ergo, there is no constant to compare the findings against (Chesney-Lind and Shelden 1998). How can one explain why the working-class commit crimes when there is little empirical evidence into why the wealthy commit crime? Drug dealing is seen as a working-class crime, as only very few gain true financial success- and those that do aren't investigated by police due to classist biases in England (Özbay 2003). Another criticism of strain theory is from Jensen (1995), who found that juveniles are less interested in their future in recent decades. So, Merton (1938) cannot explain their deviance if their strain does not exist. If they are not interested in their monetary future, juveniles are less likely to be interested in gaining money illegally. A contradiction therein is that many children in county lines are coerced and threatened into doing it (Stone 2018; Wroe 2021). Children are not willingly committing county lines offences. This links in perfectly to Agnew's (1995) newer *general strain theory* (GST) and children.

Agnew (1984) believed children want short-term goals and immediate gratification, such as friendship and sporting achievements (see also Elliott and Voss 1974). Children do not care for the *American Dream* and juvenile delinquency ergo cannot be explained by strain theory. While we know there are limitations to financial success, they are not empirically measurable- even if children did experience them. Therefore, we cannot have definitive evidence to refer to here. GST blames most interactions for crime, listing reasons for strain from everywhere: financial unhappiness, anxiety with peers, general depression, and sudden trigger events (such as family deaths) are all listed as strains (Lin 2011). Crime is noted as a "*coping strategy*" (Lin 2011, p. 36). This is a completely illegitimate claim, as people with mental illnesses are more likely to experience crimes themselves, than commit them (Pettit et al. 2013). If strains can come from anywhere, then you could list anything as a factor of crime, leaving Agnew's GST completely unjustified. That being said, Merton's original (1938) theory has a genuinely good basis for understanding how economic strains on an individual influences their type of crime and frequency thereof. There are many close links between Merton's strain theory and structural Marxist theories too.

The most prominent Marxist theory describes how crime is a construct created by the upper-classes- *bourgeois*- to subjugate the poor- *proletariat*: the idea that crimes themselves are not a social contract as we know them but a set of rules instilled by the powerful (Spitzer 1983). This claim lacks a lot of validity and would not be helpful conceptualising county lines. However, structuralist Marxism is useful to us. The focus on class divide and material want is imperative to understanding the complexity of financially based crimes. Marx decided that production of goods creates production of crime (Colvin and Pauly 1983). Material creation is material idolisation: the formation of money and the apparent

wonders it buys (Marx and Engels 1967), promoting high-roller lifestyles which are common in drug dealing. This directly connects with Merton's (1938; 1968) ideas on hedonistic crime, and how they are inspired by financial strain and the American Dream. When we focus on juvenile delinquency, a large amount of crime surrounding drugs and gangs can be explained using structural Marxism. Peer association in juveniles is caused by previous socialisation experiences in "*objective class relations*" (Colvin and Pauly 1983, p. 514) subconsciously set for them. These bonds are created on negative ideological similarities; a distaste of class struggles and greed both encourage crime under Marx's theories (1863). Negative ideological bonds create a pattern of repeat offending (Elliot, Ageton, and Canter 1979). These peers find each other and form their own ideological structure and norms- akin to Merton's ideas of assimilation. When this happens, they alienate themselves from authority and focus on delinquency (Etzioni 1970). We can interpret this as a clear introduction of gangs to society. Being a gang-related crime, county lines followed suit. This alienation is also caused by a lack of parental sternness, when dealing with their child's delinquency (Bowles and Gintis 1976). This is due to their lack of structural power in the workplace; parents with low paying jobs are more likely to be in subordinate positions in their workplace hierarchy, leading to a lower self-esteem and an inability to handle their child's immoral behaviour (Colvin and Pauly 1983). Alienation aside, this early formation of gangs are more likely to have bad experiences with authority and police anyway. The bond between working-class children and police is a shared experience based on past events (Hirschi 1969). The police are harsher on the working-class, and thus the children are more likely to view police in a negative light. This all seems convincing, but there are infamously many criticisms of Marxist criminology. One large problem with the idea that class struggles create crime is the empirical fact that class boundaries and structure is not defined and constantly fluctuates (Edwards 1979; Braithwaite 1981). It is difficult to define the exact cause of crime if the structure you're basing it on might not even exist, or does not empirically exist in definitive boundaries. In addition, as mentioned in the ethics section of my methodology, Britain has not existed with a communist government. This means we cannot compare the ideologies against each other accurately, without understanding from experience how this country would function thereunder. Nonetheless, Marx's views on our current economic climate are vital to understanding the use of children in county lines.

Crime-consumerism stems from Marxism and is prevalent in children specifically, as they are targeted by companies in subconscious ways. Advertising on TV and billboards are aimed at children specifically, enticing them into material want (Thompson 2024). They contain bright colours, easy to understand slogans, and manipulate children into believing they need the product (Winlow and Hall 2017). This subconsciously indoctrinates children into following capitalist ideologies. Economic deprivation also

affects children specifically, as they are unable to work and so cannot provide for their families. This fills them with guilt and hatred for the class system, due to their high levels of empathy and helplessness (Ellis and Walsh 1997). County lines fills that hole of guilt and desperation, by providing the children with seemingly legitimate employment- similar to certain modern slavery examples (Warria 2017). Through indoctrinating the children into thinking they're doing something honourable for their family, child slavery is completely viable and common in county lines (Stone 2018; Williams and Finlay 2019). Crime-consumerism was advanced when Treadwell et al. (2012) studied the correlation between designer brands and public disorder, uncovering that those who wore designer brands gain respect and leadership in a deviant sense; the consumerism of designer brands ergo links to members of county lines trying to establish their power through money. The more money gained from drug dealing, the more respected brands they can buy, thus circulating the problem.

Borgatti and Foster had an exceptional and unique view on crime-consumerism in their paper on the network paradigm of explanatory mechanisms of crime (2003). They broke it down into a quadrant of factors: structural capital, contagion, resource access, and environmental shaping. Structural capital ties to county lines perfectly, meaning a lack of identification. The use of a third-party links to neutralisation theory, keeping the crime at a distance (Lacey 2007). This third-party distribution is found in county lines, so much so that online advertisement of selling drugs and promoting the specific phone line used is common (Yang 2017; Demant 2022). Dealers can share their business information without fear, due to the anonymity involved, further propelling the successfulness of county lines. This is key to sharing around the telephone number. The contagion element involved is the children themselves; children learn new ideologies from the dealers, through indoctrination and *social learning theory*- the idea that children learn behaviour from visual stimuli (Sutherland 1947; Bandura 1977). Resource access is also simply explained: the importation of drugs from major cities allows a flow of stock to dealers. With the high levels of production in London, drugs are easily imported across counties with no issues to resource access whatsoever (Coomber and Moyle 2018; Black 2020). Finally, Borgatti and Foster's (2003) addition of environmental shaping has been previously explained in our ecology section (see 3.2-6). All sociological causes for the use of children in county lines (anomie, social learning theory, and ecological theories) can come under this quadrant. This highly increases the validity of the network paradigm, understanding that the theory covers the entirety of county lines. The network paradigm could not exist without taking inspiration from contemporary criminological topic *left realism*, and its construction of criminal nexuses.

Left realism was born as a counterargument to previous anti-statist, neoliberal theories (such as Marxism) that plagued the political Left with extremism (Lea and Young 1993); these ideas are henceforth known as left idealism. Left realism also focused on tackling right-realism and supported feminist movements at the time, being used as a political tactic to attack the Right (Lea 2016). Left realism wanted to decentralise the idea that constitutional constructions were entirely at fault, such as the political state of the country and its legislation thereunder (Matthews 2010). It instead wanted to focus on the victims of crime, often forgotten by left idealism (Schwartz and Dekeseredy 1991); hidden crime statistics skewed public opinions when considering the classes of the victims- but not the criminal themselves. It was often found that both the perpetrator and the victim were working-class (ibid.; Winlow and Hall 2016). This is due to a multitude of factors, ranging from sociological ideas such as anomie, to economic structure. Working-class people experience economic deprivation, forcing them into legitimising their own illegal businesses to make easy money (Young 1999); the concept therein is that the decline of the welfare state is directly proportional to the number and scale of illegitimate businesses. The realist approach to economic structures understands that complete deconstruction of the economy and government would lead to a collapsing anarchist state, despite idealist intentions (de Haan 1990). Instead, the current economic structure we have incentivises illegitimate work: the escalating market disapproves of honest business, with the majority of extreme wealth being accumulated through exploitation (Antonopoulos and Hall 2014). Left realism, in this sense, directly tackles county lines. County lines is a business model created to exploit those powerless, while legitimising itself as a rebellion against the state. The majority of county lines operations are run by working-class criminals, abusing working-class addicts and children; this directly correlates to contemporary realist theories (see Schwartz and Dekeseredy 1991). It is evidently clear that redistribution of wealth and power would reduce crime, especially drug dealing (Winlow and Hall 2016). If we were to decrease relative economic deprivation, the need to perform illegitimate business lowers- and thus, county lines disappears.

The economic theories aforementioned provide a vital explanation to county lines: capitalist consumerism breeds material want and greed in economically deprived areas. Greed emerged from monetary dissatisfaction, directly linked to a deviance into drug dealing (Agnew et al. 1996). This dissatisfaction is created when there is a lack of opportunities for those impoverished. Winlow and Hall (2020) make an evidence-based response to this deprivation in Marxist alignment, claiming redistribution of wealth would put an end to financially-focused crimes like county lines. Crime-consumerism, prevalent in those without money, forces individuals to deviate and therein lies the clear problem: economic deprivation must be rid for society to progress past drug use and distribution at

such an intense scale. We cannot forget though that this poverty shapes an individual in an ecological sense too; this interpretation of things is neatly centralised by contemporary theories as well.

Chapter 5: Understanding Both Sociological and Economic Interpretations in Contemporary Theories Relating to County Lines Itself

Contemporary theories directly relating to county lines and its practices can combine multiple theories aforementioned to create a well-rounded scope of reasons behind county lines, in both a sociological and economic sense. The importance therein is that county lines is not a phenomenon restricted to one area of study; the combination of sociological pressures on individuals in a certain economic environment produces specific crime. The same way one singular theory cannot be attributed to any one crime is how we should view county lines. Coomber and Moyle (2018) produced a significant theory on county lines, understanding it as a business model running on a supply and demand concept. This exact business model extends out of a strained society, legitimising itself as genuine income in the face of unfair capitalist structures (Agnew et al. 1996; Taylor and Potter 2013). This new form of business goes as far as creating its own professional jargon, with Coomber and Moyle (2018) centralising these new terms into the very structure of county lines; for example, members “*commute*” (p. 2) to their job, just as people in morally acceptable jobs. With these routes, there are logistics and risk-assessments involved, with dealers using empirical, scientific methods to test each route and host town to determine its safety and economic potential (Hales and Hobbs 2010). This parallels lawful businesses. These so-called businessmen collect drugs from the host city (London, eg.) to drop them off at host towns (unsaturated markets) for local dealers with good community relations to sell them at a microscale (May et al. 2005; Coomber and Moyle 2012). Host towns are selected based on their economy, and how efficient their transport links are; the importance herein is for dealers to calculate shift patterns (Hales and Hobbs 2010; Coomber and Moyle 2018)- once again, trying to equivocate their dealings to an ethical business. Another new term centralised by Coomber and Moyle (2018) is “*cuckooing*” (p. 2), where the parasitic businessman takes over the local property of a vulnerable person in social housing: usually someone with a physical or mental disability (NCA 2015), or a drug user themselves for a mutually beneficial relationship (Coliandris 2015). This is to “*optimize their profits*” (Coomber and Moyle 2018, p. 10) by not needing to pay for accommodation. It also allows an unsecure location to work from, without increasing risk- as public accommodation would. This *modus operandi* for county lines is

significant, as it separates their business from other crimes that may be socially/morally looked down upon. Our understanding of county lines already grows under these new terms, centralising the idea and statutorily defining county lines. Understanding and defining the practices allows us to discover the reasons behind them. For example, the displacement of a large-scale supplier to local dealers creates anonymity (NCA 2015; HM Government 2016). This links to both neutralisation theory (see Sykes and Matza 1957), and the structural capital of the network paradigm of crime (Borgatti and Foster 2003). Coomber and Moyle (2018) makes a point of how the lack of proximity between the CEOs of county lines and the actual crime of possession with intent to supply encourages these CEOs to grow their business and increase the frequency thereof. There is also a very viable explanation for county lines in ecological terms, in Coomber and Moyle's (2018) paper. Access to exploitation in economically deprived areas is easier than in financially secure locations (Wakeman 2016). If drugs are being transported to users in poorer areas where there is more social housing and people with disabilities, cuckooing becomes inherently easier. Migration of these vulnerable people to areas with social housing can be linked to anomie theory and the deinstitutionalisation of social morals. Victims of cuckooing are often isolated and therefore cannot experience community goals and social norms; they lose concept of laws and morals in their own subcultural environment (Tymoshenko 2022). These victims are often drug users themselves, greatly due to their finances, and so this relationship becomes skewed in the media (Coomber and Moyle 2018; NCA 2015). Of course, being drug users themselves, we can see here a deinstitutionalisation of norms in those practically enabling county lines.

Anomie theory (Merton 1954) is greatly focused on the constantly migrating population in certain areas, and with social housing pushing people further out from their hometowns, we can define these economically deprived areas as migration zones (Park and Burgess 1915; Power 2012). Migration areas were also a key point in Chicago School theory, showing Coomber and Moyle's (2018) interpretation was totally well-rounded in a sociological aspect. As previously discussed (see c3.5-6), migration zones experience anomie at a disproportionately high level (Park and Burgess 1915; Shaw and McKay 1971). At a national scale, a zonal model could prove that migration and relative poverty zones around major cities are also the host towns for county lines (*Fig. 1*, and *Fig. 2*). Coomber and Moyle (2018) do well to point it out, and make use of mapping host towns and routes taken by suppliers (*Fig. 1*). Ecological and anomie theory are both joined together under this paper, understanding the link between a weak social environment and isolation from community morals. Coomber and Moyle's (2018) paper on county lines is a combination of multiple theories, creating a well-rounded explanation for county lines. It has great validity, being from two well-known authors in the criminological community, referencing studies (such as Hales and Hobbs 2010) that are empirically accurate and unbiased. It provides centralised definitions

for the *modus operandi* of county lines, to help us understand the occurrences better. Third-party distribution is also explained here as a business model, with the additional bonus of anonymity. Other criminological theories aforementioned (Sykes and Matza 1957; Borgatti and Foster 2003) provide explanations for the need for anonymity in greater depth (see c3.7). Ecological and sociological theories are centralised in this paper, combining anomie with zonal models. There is little left to discuss or advance on this paper, extracting sources from multiple empirical studies to prove its point with clear evidence.

Another vital contemporary conclusion of county lines was authored by Andell and Pitts (2018), presenting county lines as a business born from the glorification of gang culture. As a multi-agency, local study into the exploitation of children in gangs, this paper proves useful to understanding the evolutionary tactics of delinquent groups into organised crime (NCA 2017). It focuses on the birth itself of county lines, and how this business model came about. Described as a “*franchising deal*” (Andell and Pitts 2018), county lines didn’t appear out of nowhere. It’s clear its roots are in economic deprivation, and tackling authority to establish oneself as a genuine entrepreneur. An unknown drug dealer even described county lines as a “*pyramid selling technique*” (ibid.), relating the tactics therein to a legitimised business. The same way a company has a hierarchy and labour divisions is found in county lines operations. The reason behind the ease to create an illegitimate business is outlined in this paper too: employees are available plentifully. The unnamed town experiencing mass county lines in this study was subject to frequent migrating communities, with many being immigrants. The children were left uneducated and unable to speak English as schools reached capacity, leaving some to be street educated instead (Pitts 2012). A lack of education and alienation leads to anomie and isolation (Achterberg et al. 2017). Delinquency caused by anomie descends from immigration to new societies (Spergal et al 1994). It was a natural progression for these children to be involved in crime.

Anomie is key in Andell and Pitts’ (2018) explanation of the introduction of county lines. One of their main points is on the institutionalisation of gangs into a single entity, flowing crime with ease. The NCA (2023) reported over 12,500 arrests and 23,000 disruptions involving OCGs. With these high rates of OCG disruption, gangs involved in county lines work on a hierarchical basis efficiently, giving long-term and profit earning members opportunities to rise the ranks. This internalisation of members creates a distinct, unchanging moral code between members (Hagedorn 2008). The gang is completely centralised and its morals are embedded into every member that works therein. This is a clear connection to Merton’s (1938; see also Brown 2022) ideas on deinstitutionalisation of social norms and the assimilation of delinquency into internalised morals. Not only this, but these children were brought

into the country at a time where gang culture was at its most glorified. Popular culture perpetuated gang culture to seem exciting and positive, promoting the social prestige of gang members (ibid.). Delinquent groups are formed with the seemingly common goal of fame and power. While general delinquency itself is not a significant harm to greater society, it evolves (Densley and Harding 2018). Gang-affiliated graffiti evolves into territorial claims and with it, comes territorial violence. This is Andell and Pitts' (2018) first explanation for county lines: mutation of gangs. Petty violence further extends to identity crises and an escalation to complete gang solidarity, willing to do anything to protect the public perception of said gang (Pitts 2016). Therefore, this violence becomes overwhelming and new tactics must be centralised; by transporting their business to other towns, this violence is essentially avoided. It's a smarter and less dangerous way of operating. In addition, taking over multiple towns is a clear evolution from local drug dealing. Gangs constantly perpetuate and wish to deviate more and more, performing more serious crimes over time (Dorn et al. 1992; Klein and Maxson 2006). County lines is a clear progression here, giving local gangs the opportunity to become more successful and notorious. Another way these OCGs evolved into county lines is by incorporating old tactics into their new methods. Traditionally, drug users would travel to cities with oversaturated markets to buy drugs in bulk to distribute to their friends and family, or use themselves (Andell and Pitts 2018). This is considered a freelance market, which has now progressed into a "business model" (Curtis and Wendel 2014, p. 124; Johnson et al. 1992). This was economically beneficial for the user. Now, the financial gain of the supplier and customer approval is prioritised. Users find it easier to order drugs to their hometown, instead of having to travel long distances just for narcotics (Curtis and Wendel 2014). These old practices- the freelance model- have evolved into a delivery service, on par with legitimate vendors.

Contemporary theories on county lines offer us a brilliant scope of multiple theories, centralised into one paper. This is the true benefit of contemporary papers, taking inspiration from multiple historical fields of study to provide well-rounded explanations for crime. Coomber and Moyle (2018) does a brilliant job at centralising new terms into the world of policing county lines, offering multiple explanations for the *modus operandi*; this ranges from referencing neutralisation theory and its ties to anonymity, to understanding anomie in a modern sense. Anomie theory strikes through both of these contemporary understandings, explaining the deinstitutionalisation of immigrants' moral codes and the progression into delinquency. It also offers us an understanding of assimilating new norms (as seen in Andell and Pitts' 2018 paper). Ecological and economic theories are also centralised by these new perspectives. The host towns, in which county lines takes place, are chosen through logistical analysis of relative economic deprivation and through this, legitimises the business into patterns of shift work and incorporates locals' wants and needs. There is much overlap with these two interpretations, but

each has their own way of exploring different aspects of county lines, with Coomber and Moyle (2018) focusing on cuckooing, and Andell and Pitts (2018) looking into the actual birth of county lines. These are both valid and useful contemporary theories.

Chapter 6: Further Discussion & Conclusions

Having discussed all relevant sociological and economic theories to county lines drug dealing, one thing is for certain: it cannot be defined by a single centralised theory, but only an amalgamation of multiple throughout time. This is where the previously mentioned contemporary explanations are useful, combining multiple understandings of anomie, and ecological theories. We can interpret multiple theories here, combining the knowledge we know. Even in classical schools of criminology, understanding a criminal as purely hedonistic but logical helps us understand many things today (Roshier 1989); for example, the whole idea of strain theory is that a criminal wants what they cannot achieve. This hedonism drives them to commit crime, while evaluating a pain-pleasure principle (O'Brien 2008). This pain-pleasure principle is unraveled in Coomber and Moyle's (2018) interpretation of county lines routes and the selection of host towns depending on travel time and local economy. It's clear all these theories help explain county lines when combined. Classical theories open the door to more interpretations of society and its relationship with poverty- something which is undoubtedly the cause of county lines. Looking at Marxist theories and ecological relations to deviancy and poverty, the personal economy of an individual inspires them to either conform to or deviate from shared morals. This leads to financially driven crimes such as county lines. It's indisputable, under Marxist and realist theory, that complete redistribution of wealth would halt county lines (Winlow and Hall 2020). Most drug users struggle with poverty (Manhica et al. 2020), and without buyers, businesses fail. Ergo, no drug users means no wide scale drug dealing, removing county lines as an illegitimate business venture. Both structural Marxist theories, alongside left realist critiques of its idealism, could be used to explain the business side of county lines. The escalation, evolution, and incorporation of new tactics are parallel with wanting more profit due to poverty (Andell and Pitts 2018). Although this may be true, we must understand county lines from the criminal's perspective.

The importance of Merton's (1938) interpretations of anomie and strain should not go unrecognised. These are undoubtedly the true cause of county lines. Economic deprivation does not force a person into crime, opposed to what Agnew (1995) might suggest in his GST. There are many people who live in poverty and do not deviate massively. An individual's interaction with society and economic strains give them a choice to either adapt or exploit. However, to those experiencing deep anomie and assimilation of new norms, they are not committing crime. To them, county lines is a legitimate business venture and we cannot judge them for experiencing deinstitutionalisation. Anomie gives us an insight into the criminal subculture and their newly formed morals, violating our own. Merton's theories pose a question: who decided our version of morals is the only acceptable one? If drug users are to choose to commit crime and be victims in society's eyes, then they themselves should be held accountable—not the enablers. Unfortunately, every person in this country must understand that laws are put in place to protect people and have complete control over our actions and morals, yet those deviating might not understand this as the unopposable truth. As for economic strain, while it may not specifically force an individual into crime, it does inspire a lot of negativity: greed, jealousy, and anger (Lin 2011). Here, it is not economic deprivation that causes crime, but the extreme juxtaposition between those in extreme wealth and those in poverty. Even the strain between comfortably working-class people and those wealthy inspires negative emotions (ibid.; Agnew et al. 1996). We must stop consumerism at this intense scale, and stop the extremely wealthy from exploiting the working-class for their own profit; it essentially sets a bad example for those pursuing legitimate businesses. This is reflected in county lines and its use of children as slaves.

We have already made efforts in preventing child exploitation in county lines, with the introduction of acts such as the *Modern Slavery Act 2015* (MSA). Some county lines is, by definition, child slavery, through the deployment of debt bondage (Bales et al. 2009; Wroe 2021). This is when someone is forcefully indebted to a criminal and must work for free to get out of debt. The MSA allowed for two distinct definitions for slavery and trafficking offences, providing a framework for sentencing. This is positive as there is no tribulation in court or sidestepping slavery to different offences, such as assault or coercive behaviour (Dunhill et al. 2020). Somewhere we could improve here is our legal definition of *child slave* itself, due to its multiple definitions throughout different acts (Van de Glind and Kooijmans 2008). In the MSA, there are no actual statutes referring to children themselves; only "*child victims of slavery*" (Modern Slavery Act 2015, S1). This is dismissive of children affected by county lines. If there was a centralised act that defined county lines related terms, even down to something as basic to define as child slavery, it could improve the judicial system by reducing confusion and providing guidelines for sentencing. Child slavery is technically already being tackled, with the introduction of a *Modern Slavery*

Innovation Fund (MSIF), being kickstarted in 2018 with £5 million to prevent child victimisation (Home Office 2018). This appears to be a vital step towards tackling child slavery in the United Kingdom in all forms. Instead, domestic slavery is completely forgotten and resources mainly go to tackling international human trafficking routes and slavery internally in other countries (Dunhill et al. 2020; Home Office 2021b). This is completely useless at preventing child exploitation in county lines, as this fund is more focused on “*diplomatic lobbying*” (Home Office 2022) than domestic slavery in alternative methods. There needs to be more visibility for those being groomed into, and experiencing, county lines. The only positive in the MSIF is its focus on victim support and recovery; this pillar has the biggest portion of funding from the program proportionally (ibid.). Children were successfully educated on human trafficking and how to avoid it, hopefully saving some from county lines (Home Office 2021b). Despite this, the outcome in preventing international child slavery was rated lowest in terms of success (ibid.). This disparity in data shows that domestic slavery has somewhat been successfully stopped, as the biggest failure was specifically international slavery (trafficked into the UK) while domestic education thereon was improved. The improvement in human trafficking education came from multi-agency work with the National Society for the Prevention of Cruelty to Children (NSPCC). Multi-agency work is desperately needed to prevent county lines. County lines desperately relies on the use of child exploitation, and if we tackle that, the world of drug dealing would have to evolve past the current model we have. School absences are not regularly reported to the police or social services (Sturrock and Holmes 2015). We could improve this by increasing the reporting rate and putting more pressure on the police to investigate whether county lines exploitation is the cause. In conclusion, there are many historical theories that can still apply to county lines. Hedonism rules those impoverished, and the strain their greed creates is unbearable when looking upon those fortunate and manipulative enough to exploit the masses into profit. The current market disapproves of honest work, so this exploitation is expected in our environment (Antonopoulos and Hall 2014).

Hedonism is a vital aspect to understanding county lines; if a human has innate materialism, they are to do what they wish to achieve it. Successful drug businesses make living a more fun life easier, connecting classical theories to modern-day county lines. These individuals performing county lines are, in their own way, legitimising their businesses and paralleling those moguls who exploit, unnoticed to our moral codes. If social norms were innate in every person, we would not need to worry about deviant behaviour (Merton 1938). The assimilation of a new moral code does not put blame on these individuals, but should make us wonder whether county lines is just another legitimate business that exploits the masses. It can be understood that successful CEOs and kingpins exploiting children are no different by definition, but by morals (Hirschi 1969; UKPGA 2015). Drug users are both victims and

criminals, meaning the only true victim here are the masses of children forced into slavery. If we were to liberate these children through new legislative definitions, better education, and more multi-agency work, county lines would be on par with legal ventures. It works on the basis of supply and demand, hiring workers and figuring out logistically where the most profit is. County lines is ultimately a business model- a pyramid scheme- with a CEO and employees; we should not judge their own subcultural moral code, although national legislation would agree with it. We must understand it from their perspective: deprivation is unfair, and those who rebel against social norms and profit financially are the winners.

References

Achterberg, P., de Koster, W., and van der Waal, J. (2017) 'A science confidence gap: education, trust in scientific methods, and trust in scientific institutions in the United States, 2014', *Public Understanding of Science*, 26(6), pp. 704-720.

Acker, C. (2010) 'How crack found a niche in the American ghetto: The historical epidemiology of drug-related harm.', *BioSocieties*, 5(1), pp. 70-88.

Agnew, R. (1984) 'Goal achievement and delinquency', *Sociology and Social Research*, 68, pp. 435-451.

Agnew, R. (1995) 'The Contribution of Social-Psychological Strain

Agnew, R., Cullen, F., Burton, V., Evans, T., and Dunaway, R. (1996) 'A New Test of Classic Strain Theory', *Justice Quarterly*, 13, pp. 681-704.

Agnew, R., and Passas, N. (1997) 'The Future of Anomie Theory', *Contemporary Sociology*, 29(1), pp. 252.

Andell, P., and Pitts, J. (2018) *The End of the Line? The Impact of County Lines Drug Distribution on Youth Crime in a Target Destination*. Available at: <https://www.youthandpolicy.org/articles/the-end-of-the-line/>. (Accessed 25/04/25).

Andlin-Sobocki, P. (2005) 'Economic evidence in addiction: a review.', *European Journal of Health Economics*, doi: 10.1007/s10198-005-0282-5.

Antonopoulos, G., and Hall, S. (2014) *The death of the legitimate merchant? Small to medium-size enterprises and shady decisions in Greece during the financial crisis*, in: van Duyne, P., Harvey, J., Antonopoulos, G., Maljevic, A., Markovska, A., and von Lampe, J. (2014) *Corruption, Greed and Crime Money: Sleaze and Shady Economics in Europe and Beyond*. Nijmegen: Wolf Legal Publishers.

Antrobus, S. (2009) *Dying to Belong: An In-depth Review of Street Gangs in Britain : a Policy Report*. London: Centre for Social Justice.

Baldwin, J., Bottoms, A., and Walker, M. (1976) *The Urban Criminal: A Study in Sheffield*. London: Tavistock Publications.

Bales, K., Trodd, Z., and Williamson A. (2009) *Modern Slavery: The Secret World of 27 Million People*. London: Oneworld Publications.

Bandura, A. (1971) *Social Learning Theory*. New York, NY: General Learning Press.

Bellair, P. (2017) *Social Disorganization Theory*. Available at: <https://oxfordre.com/criminology/display/10.1093/acrefore/9780190264079.001.0001/acrefore-9780190264079-e-253>. (Accessed 21/04/25).

Bernasco, W. (2014) *Crime Journeys: Patterns of offender mobility*, in: Tonry, M., (2014) *Oxford Handbooks Online in Criminology and Criminal Justice*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Bernberg, J. (2002) 'Anomie, Social Change and Crime. A Theoretical Examination of Institutional-Anomie Theory', *The British Journal of Criminology*, 42(4), pp. 729-742.

Black, C. (2020) *Review of drugs: summary (accessible version)*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/review-of-drugs-phase-one-report/review-of-drugs-summary>. (Accessed 15/01/25).

Bloch, H. (1958) 'They Are Not Born Criminals', *Federal Probation*, 22, pp. 15.

Booth, C., and Reeder, D. (1984) *Charles Booth's descriptive map of London poverty*. London: London Topographical Society.

Borgatti, S., and Foster, P. (2003) *The Network Paradigm in Organizational Research: A Review and Typology*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications.

Bosworth, D. (1994) 'Truancy and Pupil Performance', *Education Economics*, 2(3), pp. 243–264.

Bowles, S., and Gintis, H. (1976) *Schooling in Capitalist America*. New York, NY: Basic Books.

Braithwaite, J. (1981) "The Myth of Social Class and Criminality Reconsidered", *American Sociological Review*, 46, pp. 36-57.

Brown, C., Luzmore, R., and Ophoff, J. (2022) 'Anomie in the UK? Can cultural malaise threaten the fruition of the ideas-informed society?', *Open Emerald Research*, 1(1). DOI: 10.1108/eor-01-2023-0009.

Burke, R. (2018) *An Introduction to Criminology*. Abingdon: Routledge.

Chesney-Lind, M., and Shelden, R. (1998) *Girls, Delinquency, and Juvenile Justice: The Wadsworth Contemporary Issues in Crime and Justice Series*. Belmont, CA: Wadsworth Publishing Company.

Cohen, L., and Machalek, R. (1988) 'A general theory of expropriative crime: An evolutionary ecological approach', *American Journal of Sociology*, 94(3), pp. 465–501.

Cohen, S. (2001) *States of Denial: Knowing about Atrocities and Suffering*. Cambridge: Polity Press.

Coliandris, G. (2015), 'County Lines and Wicked Problems: Exploring the Need for Improved Policing Approaches to Vulnerability and Early Intervention', *Australasian Policing*, 7, p. 26–35.

Colvin, M., and Pauly, J. (1983) 'A Critique of Criminology: Toward an Integrated Structural-Marxist Theory of Delinquency Production', *American Journal of Sociology*, 89(3), pp. 513-551.

Coomber, R., and Moyle, L. (2012) *A Rapid Appraisal of the Illicit Drug Market in Southend-on-Sea, Essex*. Plymouth: Plymouth University Drug and Alcohol Research Unit.

Coomber, R., and Moyle, L. (2017) 'The Changing Shape of Street-Level Heroin and Crack Supply in England: Commuting, Holidaying and Cuckooing Drug Dealers Across 'County Lines'', *The British Journal of Criminology*, 58(6), pp. 1323-1342.

Cooper, C., Hesketh, O., Ellis, N., and Fair, A. (2017) *A Typology of Modern Slavery Offences in the UK*. London: Home Office Stationery.

Cornish, D., and Clarke, R. (2008) *The rational choice perspective*, in: Wortley, R., and Mazerolle, L. (2008) *Environmental criminology and crime analysis*. Cullompton: Willan Publishing.

Curren, A. (2023) *Slipping the Line: The Assembled Geographies of Gang Territories*. New York, NY: Springer Publishing.

Costello, B. (2010) 'Peer Influence Toward Conformity', *Journal of Crime and Justice*, 33(1), pp. 97-116.

Curtis, R., and Wendel, T. (2014) "Toward the development of a typology of illegal drug markets", *Crime Prevention Studies*, 11, pp. 121-152.

de Haan, W. (1990) *The Politics of Redress: Crime, Punishment, and Penal Abolishment*. Cullompton: Willan Publishing.

Demant, J., and Aagesen, K. (2022) *An analysis of drug dealing via social media*. Copenhagen: University of Copenhagen.

Densley, J., and Harding, S. (2018) *Gangs in Europe*. Oxford: Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Criminology and Criminal Justice.

Dorn, N., Murji, K., and South, N. (1992) *Traffickers: Drug Markets and Law Enforcement*. New York, NY: Routledge.

Dunhill, A., Gordon, F., Kidd, A., Kirk, T., and Lundy, L. (2020) 'Responses to child victims of modern slavery in the United Kingdom: a children's rights perspective', *Child and Family Law Quarterly*, 2. Available at: <https://hull-repository.worktribe.com/OutputFile/3393563>. (Accessed 25/04/25).

Dunlap, E., Johnson, B., Kotarba, J., and Fackler, J. (2010) 'Macro-Level Social Forces and Micro-Level Consequences: Poverty, Alternate Occupations, and Drug Dealing', *Journal of Ethnicity in Substance Abuse*, 9(2), pp. 115–127.

Durkheim, E. (1951). *Suicide: A study in sociology*. New York, NY: Free Press.

Edward, R. (1979) *Contested Terrain: The Transformation of the Workplace in the Twentieth Century*. New York, NY: Basic Books.

Elliot, D., and Voss, H. (1974) *Delinquency and Dropout*. New York, NY: Lexington Books.

Elliot, D., Ageton, S., and Canter, R. (1979) "An Integrated Theoretical Perspective on Delinquent Behaviour", *Journal of Research in Crime and Delinquency*, 16, pp. 3-27.

Etzioni, A. (1970) "Compliance Theory", in: Grusky, O., and Miller, G. (1970) *The Sociology of Organizations*. New York, NY: Free Press.

Farrall, S., Gray, E., and Jones, P. (2020) 'The Role of Radical Economic Restructuring in Truancy from School and Engagement in Crime', *The British Journal of Criminology*, 60(1), pp. 118–140.

Featherstone, R., and Deflem, M. (2003) 'Anomie and Strain: Context and Consequences of Merton's Two Theories', *Sociological Inquiry*, 73(4), pp. 471-489.

Felson, R., Osgood, D., Cundiff, P., and Wiernik, C. (2018) 'Life in the Fast Lane: Drugs, Hedonistic Lifestyles, and Economic Crime', *Crime & Delinquency*, 65(9), pp. 1292-1318.

Fingarette, H. (1967) *On Responsibility*. New York, NY: Basic Books.

Gale, D. (1955) 'The Law of Supply and Demand', *Mathematica Scandinavica*, 3(1), pp. 155-169.

Gilsinan, J. (2006) 'Public Policy and Criminology: An (sic) Historical and Philosophical Reassessment', *Justice Quarterly*, 8(2), pp. 201-216.

Goodhart, D. (2017) *The Road to Somewhere: The Populist Revolt and the Future of Politics*. London: Hurst Publishers.

Hagedorn, J. (2008) *A World of Gangs, Armed Young Men and Gangsta Culture*. Minneapolis, MN: University of Minnesota Press.

Hales, G., and Hobbs, D. (2010) 'Drug Markets in the Community: A London Borough Case Study', *Trends in Organised Crime*, 13, pp. 13–30.

Han, L., Ren, Y., and Zhang, Z. (2022) "Explanation of the causes of British moral anomie during the industrial revolution-a comprehensive analysis framework based on religion, thought and education", *Cogent Arts and Humanities*, 10(2), doi: 10.1080/23311983.2023.2286072.

Hirschi, T. (1969) *Causes of Delinquency*. Berkeley and Los Angeles, CA: University of California Press.

HM Government (2016) *Ending Gang Violence and Exploitation*. London: Home Office.

Hoeben, M., Bernasco, W., Weerman, F., Pauwels, L., and van Halem, S. (2014) 'The space-time budget method in criminological research', *Crime Science*, 3(12), pp. 1–15.

Home Office (2018) *New action to tackle modern slavery and support victims*. Available at: www.gov.uk/government/news/new-action-to-tackle-modern-slavery-and-support-victim. (Accessed 25/04/25).

Home Office (2021a) *Review of drugs part two: prevention, treatment, and recovery*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/review-of-drugs-phase-two-report/review-of-drugs-part-two-prevention-treatment-and-recovery#:~:text=Although%20Part%201%20of%20the,on%20investment%20of%20%C2%A34>. (Accessed 25/04/25).

Home Office (2021b) *Modern Slavery Innovation Fund: phase 1 end term review*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/modern-slavery-innovation-fund-phase-1-end-term-review/modern-slavery-innovation-fund-phase-1-end-term-review-accessible-version>. (Accessed 25/04/25).

Home Office (2022) *Modern Slavery Fund review (2019 to 2021): findings, lessons and recommendations*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/modern-slavery-fund-review/modern-slavery-fund-review-2019-to-2021-findings-lessons-and-recommendations-accessible#:~:text=In%20some%20contexts%2C%20these%20led,private%20sector%20confederation%20supply%20chains>. (Accessed 25/04/25).

Jensen, G. (1995) 'Salvaging Structure Through Strain: A Theoretical and Empirical Critique', in: Adler, F., and Laufer, W. (1999) *The Legacy of Anomie Theory: Advances in Criminological Theory Vol.6*. New Brunswick, NJ: Transaction Publishers.

Johnson, B., Hamid, A., and Sanabria, H (1992) *Emerging Models of Crack Distribution*, in: Mieczkowski, T. (1992) *Drugs, Crime, and Social Policy: Research, Issues, and Concerns*. Boston, MA: Allyn and Bacon.

Joshi, I. (2022) 'Criminology Through the Lens of Positivism', *Indian Journal of Law and Legal Research*, 5(5).

Kaestner, R. (1997) *Does Drug Use Cause Poverty?*, in: Chaloupka, F., Grossman, M., Bickel, W., and Saffer, H. (1999) *The Economic Analysis of Substance Use and Abuse: An Integration of Econometrics and Behavioral Economic Research*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.

Kemp, P., Neale, J., and Robertson, M. (2006) 'Homelessness among problem drug users: prevalence, risk factors and trigger events.', *Health & Social Care in the Community*, 14, pp. 319-328.

Klein, M. and Maxson, C. (2006) *Street Gang Patterns and Policies*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Lacey, N. (2007) *Denial and Responsibility*. Oxford: University of Oxford Press.

Lazarsfeld, P., and Merton, R. (1954) *Friendship as a Social Process: A Substantive and Methodological Analysis*, in: Berger, M., Abel, T., and Charles, H. (1954) *Freedom and Control in Modern Society*. New York, NY: Van Nostrand.

Lea, J., and Young, J. (1993) *What is to Be Done about Law and Order?* London: Pluto Press.

Lea, J. (2016) "Left realism: A radical criminology for the current crisis", *International Journal for Crime, Justice and Social Democracy*, 5(3), pp. 53-65.

Lin, W. (2011) *General Strain Theory and Juvenile Delinquency: A Cross Cultural Study*. Tampa, FL: University of South Florida Tampa Graduate Theses and Dissertations.

London School of Economics and Political Science [LSE] (2024) *What were the poverty maps?*. Available at: <https://booth.lse.ac.uk/learn-more/what-were-the-poverty-maps>. (Accessed 17/04/25).

Lutters, W., and Ackerman, M. (1996) *An Introduction to the Chicago School of Sociology*. (Unpublished).

Manhica, H., Straatmann, V., Lundin, A., Agardh, E., and Danielsson, A. (2020) 'Association between poverty exposure during childhood and adolescence, and drug use disorders and drug-related crimes later in life', *Addiction*, 116(7), pp. 1747-1756.

Matthews, R. (2010) "The construction of 'so what?' criminology: A realist analysis", *Crime, Law and Social Change*, 54(2), pp. 125-140.

Matthews, R. (2011) 'Marxist Criminology', in *Routledge Handbook of Critical Criminology*. London: Routledge.

Marx, K. (1863) *Theories of Surplus Value*. Moscow: Progress Publishers.

Marx, K., and Engels, F. (1967) *The German Ideology*. New York, NY: International Publishers.

Mayhew, H. (1862) *London labour and the London poor*. London: Griffin Bohn.

McAra, L. (2004) *Truancy, School Exclusion and Substance Misuse*. Edinburgh: University of Edinburgh Press.

Merton, R. (1938) 'Social Structure and Anomie', *American Sociological Review*, 3(5), pp. 672–682.

Merton, R. (1954) 'Voluntary strength and fatigue', *The Journal of Physiology*, 123(3), pp. 553-564.

Merton, R. (1968) *Social theory and social structure*. New York, NY: The Free Press.

Modern Slavery Act 2015. Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2015/30/contents>. (Accessed 25/04/25).

Monahan, T. (1961) 'On the Trend in Delinquency', *Social Forces*, 40(2), pp. 158-168.

National Crime Agency [NCA] (2015) *NCA Intelligence Assessment. County Lines, Gangs, and Safeguarding*. London: National Crime Agency.

National Crime Agency [NCA] (2017) *County Lines, Violence, Exploitation & Drug Supply 2017*. London: National Crime Agency.

National Crime Agency [NCA] (2023) *A Decade of Disrupting Serious and Organised Crime*. Available at: <https://www.nationalcrimeagency.gov.uk/?view=article&id=3196:the-national-crime-agency-marks-a-decade-of-disrupting-serious-and-organised->. (Accessed 25/04/25).

O'Brien, M. (2008) *Criminology: The Key Concepts*. Abingdon: Routledge.

Oezbay, O. (2003) 'Merton's Strain Theory: Evidence From the High Schools in Ankara', *Cumhuriyet University Journal of Social Sciences*, 27(1), pp. 59-76.

O'Hagan, A., and Hamis, KM (2023) 'County lines and the impact of police response: a study of Norfolk compared with East Anglia and the nation (England and wales)', *Forensic Research and Criminology International Journal*, 11(3), pp. 94-103.

O'Hagan, A., and Long, A, (2019) 'The socioeconomic effects of organised crimes county lines on the United Kingdom community.', *Forensic Research and Criminology International Journal*, 7(5), pp. 274-280.

Olver, K., and Cockbain, E. (2021) 'Professionals' Views on Responding to County Lines-Related Criminal Exploitation in the West Midlands, UK', *Child Abuse Review*, 30(4), pp. 347-362.

O'Malley, P. (1987) 'Marxist Theory and Marxist Criminology', *Crime and Social Justice*, 29, pp. 70-87.

Office for National Statistics [ONS] (2024) *Drug misuse in England and Wales: year ending March 2024*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/review-of-drugs-phase-one-report/review-of-drugs-summary>. (Accessed 15/01/25).

Orford, S., Dorling, D., Mitchell, R., Shaw M., and Smith, G. (2002) 'Life and death of the people of London: a historical GIS of Charles Booth's inquiry', *Health & Place*, 8(1), pp. 25-35.

Park, R., Burgess, E., and McKenzie, R. (1915) *The City*. Chicago, IL: Chicago University Press.

Pettitt, B., Greenhead, S., Khalifeh, H., Drennan, V., Hart, T., Hogg, J., Borschmann, R., Mamo, E., and Moran, P. (2013) *At risk, yet dismissed: The criminal victimisation of people with mental health problems*. London: Victim Support.

Pitts, J. (2012) *Youth Crime and Criminal Victimisation amongst Somali Young People in Moss Side: A Rapid Assessment Exercise*. Manchester: Greater Manchester Police.

Pitts, J. (2016) *Critical Realism and Gang Violence*, in: Matthews, R. (2018) *What is to be Done About Crime and Punishment: Towards a Public Criminology*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.

Power, A. (2012) "Social inequality, disadvantaged neighbourhoods and transport deprivation: an assessment of the historical influence of housing policies", *Journal of Transport Geography*, 21, pp. 39-48.

Rimke, H. (2011) *The Pathological Approach to Crime: Individually Based Theories, in Criminology: Critical Canadian Perspectives*. Toronto: Pearson Education Canada.

Roshier, B. (1989) *Controlling Crime: The Classical Perspective*. Milton Keynes: Open University Press.

Sampson, R. (2019) in: Park, R., Burgess, E. (2019) *The City, 2nd Edition*. Chicago, IL: Chicago University Press.

Schwartz, M., and DeKeseredy, W. (1991) "Left realist criminology: Strengths, weaknesses and the feminist critique", *Crime, Law and Social Change*, 15, pp. 51-72.

Shaw, C., and McKay, H. (1942) *Juvenile delinquency and urban areas*. Chicago, IL: Chicago University Press.

Shaw, C., and McKay, H. (1969) *Juvenile Delinquency and Urban Areas: A Study of Rates of Delinquency in Relation to Differential Characteristics of Local Communities in American Cities*, in: Andresen, M., Brantingham, P., Kinney, J. (2010) *Classics in Environmental Criminology*. Abingdon: Routledge.

Sousa, R., and Sousa, S. (2021) *Criminals Are Made Not Born*, in: Shackelford, T., and Weekes-Shackelford, V. (2021) *Encyclopedia of Evolutionary Psychological Science*. New York, NY: Springer.

Spergel, I., Chance, R., Ehrensaft, K., Regulus, T., Kane, C., Laseter, R., Alexander, A., and Oh, S. (1994) *Gang Suppression and Intervention: Community Models Research Summary*. Washington DC, WA: Office of Juvenile Justice and Delinquency Prevention.

Spicer, J. (2021) 'Between gang talk and prohibition: The transfer of blame for County Lines', *International Journal of Drug Policy*, 87, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugpo.2020.102667>.

Spitzer, S. (1983) 'Marxist Perspectives in the Sociology of Law', *Annual Review of Sociology*, 9, pp. 103-124.

Stone, N. (2018) 'Child Criminal Exploitation: 'County Lines', Trafficking and Cuckooing', *Youth Justice*, 18(3), pp. 285-293.

Sturrock, R., and Holmes, L. (2015) *Running the Risks: The links between gang involvement and young people going missing*. London: Catch 22.

Sutherland, E. (1947) *Principles of criminology*. Philadelphia, PA: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.

Sykes, G., and Matza, D. (1957) 'Techniques of Neutralization: A Theory of Delinquency', *American Sociological Review*, 22(6), pp. 664-670.

Taylor, M., and Potter, G. (2013) 'From "Social Supply" to "Real Dealing": Drift, Friendship, and Trust in Drug-Dealing Careers', *Journal of Drug Issues*, 43(4), pp. 392-406.

Temple, A. (2020) *Excluded, Exploited, Forgotten: Childhood Criminal Exploitation and School Exclusions*. London: Just For Kids Law.

Thornton, W. (1866) 'A New Theory of Supply and Demand', *Fortnightly Review*, 6(34), pp. 420-434.

Tymoshenko, V. (2022) "Interdependence of Marginality and Anomie", *Scientific Journal of the National Academy of Internal Affairs*, 27(2), pp. 9-16.

Walklate, S. (2017) *Handbook of Victims and Victimology*. Abingdon: Taylor and Francis Group.

Walkup, J., and Bellak, L. (1999) 'Positivism and psychoanalysis: A new look at the historical record', *Psychoanalytic Review*, 86(2), pp. 163-174.

Warria, A. (2017) 'International and African Regional Instruments to Protect Rights of Child Victims of Transnational Trafficking', *Victims & Offenders*, 12, pp. 682-699.

White, R., and Haines, F. (2004) *Crime and Criminology: An Introduction*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Wiles, P., and Costello, A. (2000) *The "Road to Nowhere": The Evidence for Travelling Criminals*. London: Home Office.

Williams, A., and Finlay, F. (2019) 'County lines: how gang crime is affecting our young people', *Archives of Disease in Childhood*, 104, pp. 730-732.

Wilson, G. (2017) Exploring County Lines in Suffolk. Unpublished (Internal review).

Wilson, J. (1975) *Thinking About Crime*. New York: Basic Books.

Wilson, W. (1987) *The truly disadvantaged*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.

Windle J., and Briggs D. (2015) 'It's like working away for two weeks', The Harms Associated with Young Drug Dealers Commuting from a Saturated London Drug Market', *Crime Prevention and Community Safety*, 17, pp. 105-119.

Winlow, S., and Hall, S. (2016) "Realist criminology and its discontents", *International Journal for Crime, Justice and Social Democracy*, 5(3), pp. 80-94.

Wroe, L. (2021) 'Young people and "county lines": a contextual and social account', *Journal of Children's Services*, 16(1), pp. 39-55.

Ugwudike, P. (2015) *An Introduction to Critical Criminology*. Bristol: Policy Press.

UK Public General Acts [UKPGA] (2009) *Policing and Crime Act 2009*. Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2009/26/part/4>. (Accessed 23/12/24).

UK Public General Acts [UKPGA] (2015) *Modern Slavery Act 2015*. Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2015/30/section/3/enacted>. (Accessed 25/04/25).

United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime [UNODC] (2006) *Cocaine: Wholesale, street prices and purity levels*. Available at: https://www.unodc.org/pdf/WDR_2006/wdr2006_chap5_cocaine.pdf. (Accessed 15/01/25).

United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime [UNODC] (2021) *Price and Purity*. Available at: https://www.unodc.org/documents/data-and-analysis/WDR2021/8.1_Prices_an_purities_of_Drugs.pdf. (Accessed 15/01/25).

Valasik, M. (2014) 'Classical Criminology', in *The Encyclopedia of Criminology and Criminal Justice*. Oxford: Blackwell Publishing.

Valentine, K., and Fraser, S. (2008) 'Trauma, damage and pleasure: Rethinking problematic drug use', *International Journal of Drug Policy*, 19(5), pp. 410-416.

Van de Glind, H., and Kooijmans, J. (2008) 'Modern-Day Child Slavery', *Children & Society*, 22(3), pp. 150-166.

Vila, B. (1994) 'A general paradigm for understanding criminal behavior: Extending evolutionary ecological theory', *Criminology*, 32(3), pp. 311-359.

Yang, X., and Luo, J. (2017) 'Tracking Illicit Drug Dealing and Abuse on Instagram

Using Multimodal Analysis', *ACM Transactions on Intelligent Systems and Technology*, 8(4), Article 58.

Young, J. (1999) *The Exclusive Society: Social Exclusion, Crime and Difference in Late Modernity*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications.

Appendices

Figure One [Fig. 1]: Map of the United Kingdom, indicating host towns for county lines and transport routes (Coomber and Moyle 2018)

Figure Two [Fig. 2]: Map of social housing density in the United Kingdom (CORE 2011)